

Reforming the General Medical Council

legislative framework – Consultation

Response

Department of Health and Social Care

Date: 12 June 2026

Submitted by: Vsevolod Shabad, independent researcher on NHS and public-sector risk governance, and Principal Enterprise Architect at a FTSE 100 company. This submission is made in a personal capacity and does not represent the views of any employer, institution, or organisation. The author's published work includes an empirical analysis of risk governance across 171 NHS trusts and a body of work on NHS board assurance, decision-making, and patient-safety culture.

This response comments on the draft General Medical Council Order 2026 (Department of Health and Social Care & The Scottish Government, 2026) only where the author can claim specific competence: the architecture of the regulator's information, decision and learning systems (how it measures performance, escalates risk, communicates warnings, learns from failure, and guards against conflicts of function). Within that scope, the five points below identify features of the draft Order that will, predictably, reproduce the failures the reform is meant to prevent. Each is a property of the architecture, not of the conduct of the regulator or any individual within it. The analysis draws on the author's published empirical work on NHS and public-sector risk governance (Shabad, 2025a, 2025b, 2026a, 2026b, 2026c) and the author's experience in the enterprise architecture of large companies.

The same scope sets the limits of this response. It does not address the professional-title changes (Leng Review recommendations 1 and 9) or the recommendations of the Lord Mann review, which turn on clinical practice and discrimination policy judgements rather than on governance architecture.

Each of the five points is actionable on its own, and the architectural remedy across them is the same: build the quality that the system needs into the structure, rather than ask the people inside it to supply it. Because the draft Order is secondary legislation, each recommendation is framed as a statutory duty for the Order itself, leaving the operational detail (the registry, the metrics, the interface) to the rules and guidance that the Order delegates to the regulator under Articles 10 and 42. The first point is foundational: it determines whether any learning mechanism in the Order will work at all.

1. Separating learning from deterrence: the honest record (Article 16(4)(b))

Article 16(4)(b) requires the regulator to identify "points of learning" from fitness-to-practise cases and propose how to address them. This is the right intention, but the architecture defeats it. The fitness-to-practise channel, meant to generate learning, is the same channel that carries enforcement consequences (conditions, suspension, removal). Where the channel that collects information about a failure also determines the penalty for it, documenting a governance failure honestly becomes irrational for the individual and the employer; the record stays technically accurate but silent on the systemic contributors that matter most (Shabad, 2026b). A culture of fear suppresses exactly the disclosure that learning requires (Francis, 2015). The safety-science tradition of high-reliability organisations, applied to medicine, holds that effective risk management depends on a reporting culture, and that a reporting culture, in turn, depends on a just culture that separates blameless from blameworthy acts, so that reporting happens at all (Reason, 2000).

UK health policy already accepts this principle elsewhere. The Health Services Safety Investigations Body operates a statutory "safe space" precisely so that safety learning can be surfaced without feeding individual liability ("Health and Care Act", 2022), and the Patient Safety Incident Response Framework reorients NHS incident response toward learning rather than blame (NHS England, 2022). The draft Order does not extend that settled principle into professional regulation. As drafted, "points of learning" will systematically under-record near-misses and systemic patterns (the weak signals that matter) because the only route for them runs through the enforcement machine.

Recommendation. The GMC is an enforcement body, so it cannot adopt the HSSIB "safe space" wholesale: facts about a clinical failure must stay available to the case in which they

arise, both for the regulator and for the professional's own defence. The principle can still be realised one level up. Case examiners and panels should have a statutory duty, when a fitness-to-practise case exposes a system-level contributor (for example, an IT failure or a structural staffing pressure bearing on a clinical error), to log that contributor in a dedicated learning registry that is analysed and published in aggregate, so that NHS England and providers can act on the pattern. This registry sits alongside the individual determination, not in place of it: the same systemic factors remain fully available to the professional as mitigation. The aim is to extract the systemic signal that individual incentives otherwise suppress, without building a parallel, non-attributable record of doubts about named individuals. This converts the Article 16(4)(b) duty from a statement of intent into an architectural property: the learning function is separated from the deterrence function at the level of analysis, not by hiding facts from the case where they belong.

2. Reporting measures static attainment, not adaptive capacity (Articles 16, 18, 34, 42)

Article 16(1)(b) requires a statistical analysis of "arrangements that the regulator has put in place", and Article 16(4)(c) requires an assessment of "the effectiveness of its arrangements". Articles 34 and 42 set registration standards and periodic assessment against a fixed standard. The common feature is that all of these measure static attainment (whether a standard has been met at a given moment) rather than adaptive capacity, meaning whether the regulator and the professionals it assesses are improving quickly enough to keep pace with a changing risk environment.

Where threats keep evolving, meeting a fixed standard is not holding position but slipping behind it: an organisation has to keep improving simply to stay level (Shabad, 2026a). An empirical analysis of 171 NHS trusts shows the consequence: the largest, best-resourced organisations did not outperform smaller ones on mandatory assurance. A bigger organisation has a larger surface to defend, so the same effort buys less ground. Resources spent meeting a static standard produce attainment at a single moment, not the rate of improvement that keeping pace demands. A static attainment metric cannot see this. It records whether a standard is met now, not whether performance is improving or decaying as the environment changes. A report that an arrangement is "in place" therefore cannot tell a regulator whether its practice is improving or standing still while the risks around it grow. The result is an assurance trap, in which a compliant report masks a degrading operational reality.

Recommendation. Article 16 should require the regulator to publish a velocity signal alongside its static reporting: trajectory metrics showing whether key capabilities (case-handling, assessment, escalation) are improving, static, or degrading over time, not only whether arrangements exist. The strategic plan (Article 18) should be assessed against the same trajectory, so that the question becomes whether the regulator is improving faster than the risks that it manages, not whether it has met a fixed target.

3. The three-stage process rewards defensible delay (Articles 50–52, 56–57)

The three-stage fitness-to-practise process is shot through with discretion ("where the regulator considers appropriate" recurs at each stage), and Article 50(4) prevents referral to a case examiner until the professional has made written representations or the response window has expired. Article 57 allows urgent interim measures to bypass this, but leaves the threshold for "urgency" to the unstructured judgement of the individual.

This is a familiar architecture. Where no one has stated, at the deciding level, the objective a decision should serve, asking for more evidence is easy to defend and acting on a partial signal is not, so waiting becomes the rational individual choice even when waiting costs more than acting (Shabad, 2026d). The result is decision latency: a warning becomes a history lesson, and the absence of a decision goes unrecorded because only decisions taken leave a trace. The reform speeds the process mechanically; it does not remove the incentive to defer defensibly.

Recommendation. The draft Order should require the regulator to publish a transparent risk-escalation threshold instrument (analogous to the National Patient Safety Alert system; Shabad, 2026e), defining explicit, non-discretionary triggers (for example, specified charges or clinical thresholds) that require a time-bound triage decision rather than a discretionary one. Where such a threshold is crossed, the Article 50(4) wait for representations should be compressed or bypassed in favour of an interim measure, with representations heard immediately afterwards. This sequence is consistent with Article 6 ECHR, as the fair hearing is preserved through prompt post-decision review rather than being removed. Article 16 reporting should publish the elapsed time from the initial risk signal to the first registration measure (median and 90th percentile) and should report on cases where no decision was reached, not only on cases decided, making inaction as visible as action.

4. The public register must stay verifiable against AI misrepresentation (Article 9)

Article 9 gives the regulator broad discretion over how it discloses registration information. The public register is the authoritative record of who is licensed to practise, and patients increasingly reach it not directly but through AI search intermediaries that scrape and reprocess it. Once the register is mediated this way, a patient can be shown stale or fabricated verification of a professional's status: a suspension not yet reflected, or a registration confirmed for someone who holds none. The Order treats disclosure as a one-way publication act and is silent on the integrity of the register once it leaves the regulator's own interface, which is precisely where the chain of trust the register exists to protect can break (Shabad, 2026a, 2026c). This point concerns the integrity of the status the register reports. A separate question (how much detail the regulator should publish about its impairment criteria) involves a real transparency trade-off that this response does not try to settle.

Recommendation. The draft Order should widen the Article 9 disclosure power to cover the machine-readable integrity of the register, not only the fact of publication. The regulator should disseminate registration status through a real-time, verifiable interface that prevents third parties from caching or misrepresenting a stale status, and should set terms of use for the platforms that reprocess its data. This keeps the register authoritative at the point a patient actually consults it, by whatever route they reach it.

5. The regulator should not assess its own effectiveness (Article 16(4)(c))

Article 16(4)(c) asks the regulator to assess "the effectiveness of its arrangements" itself. This is a conflict of functions, not a question of good faith: the body that designs the arrangements, applies them, and reports on them is asked to mark its own homework. The draft Order already applies separation of duties well elsewhere: the case-examiner and panel structure, and the Medical Tribunals Service, separate investigation from adjudication. The same principle should reach the effectiveness assessment, and the architecture for it already exists. The Professional Standards Authority reviews the GMC's performance every year against its Standards of Good Regulation under the "National Health Service Reform and Health Care Professions Act" (2002). A fresh self-assessment under Article 16(4)(c) adds nothing to that external review; it sits beside it as a parallel, self-interested account. Where an actor's

interests can diverge from the system's, the durable remedy is to separate the function from the stake rather than to rely on character (Shabad, 2026b).

Recommendation. The Article 16(4)(c) effectiveness assessment should be discharged through, or independently validated by, the Professional Standards Authority's existing annual performance review, rather than self-certified by the regulator in parallel. This adds no new body or burden; it routes an existing duty to the independent reviewer who already holds the mandate.

Summary

The draft Order moves medical regulation in the right direction, and several of its structural choices (separating investigation from adjudication, a single statutory objective, periodic assessment) are sound. The five points above are architectural refinements that would make the model deliver what it intends: learn honestly by separating learning from deterrence (1); report on improvement and not only attainment (2); make timely decisions and not only defensible ones (3); keep the public register verifiable as patients reach it through AI intermediaries (4); and let someone other than the regulator judge its effectiveness (5). The first is the one that most deserves attention, because it determines whether every other learning mechanism in the Order will work at all.

Mapping to consultation questions

This response is submitted as free text but maps onto the consultation questions below. The five points are scoped to governance architecture; the questions on professional titles, education and training, clinical grounds for action, and the Lord Mann review recommendations fall outside that scope and are not addressed.

Consultation question	Addressed in	In brief
Governance – Do you agree that the provisions in parts 2 to 4 (disclosure of information, guidance, annual reports) enable GMC to carry out its	Sections 1, 2, 4, 5	Article 16 reporting should capture systemic learning (1) and report improvement, not only attainment (2); the Article 16(4)(c) effectiveness assessment should be routed to the PSA's existing

Consultation question	Addressed in	In brief
governance and operating framework functions appropriately?		annual review (5); the Article 9 disclosure power should cover register integrity against AI misrepresentation (4).
Fitness to practise – proceedings – Do you agree that the fitness-to-practise powers and duties for GMC and MTS are sufficient and proportionate?	Sections 1, 3	The "points of learning" duty needs a learning channel separated from deterrence (1); the three-stage process should carry a non-discretionary escalation threshold so that timely action is as defensible as delay (3).
Interim registration measures – Do you agree the panel's power should extend to interim measures during registration proceedings?	Section 3	Supported; the Article 57 "urgency" threshold should be set by an explicit, published trigger rather than left to unstructured judgement, with Article 6 ECHR preserved through a prompt post-decision hearing.
Registration – Do you agree the draft order enables GMC to carry out its registration functions sufficiently?	Section 2	The fixed registration standards (Article 34) measure static attainment; a trajectory signal would show whether capability is keeping pace with a changing risk environment.

References

Department of Health and Social Care, & The Scottish Government. (2026). *HEALTH CARE AND ASSOCIATED PROFESSIONS. The General Medical Council Order 2026.*

<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/69c29e2013101e9908704b9b/draft-general-medical-council-order-2026-version-for-consultation.pdf>

Francis, R. (2015). *Freedom to speak up.* https://freedomtospeakup.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/F2SU_web.pdf

Health and Care Act (2022). <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2022/31/contents>

National Health Service Reform and Health Care Professions Act (2002).

<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/17/contents>

NHS England. (2022). *Patient Safety Incident Response Framework*. Retrieved 12 June 2026

from <https://www.england.nhs.uk/patient-safety/patient-safety-insight/incident-response-framework/>

Reason, J. (2000). Human error: models and management. *BMJ*, 320(7237), 768.

<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.320.7237.768>

Shabad, V. (2025a). *Cognitive Blind Spots in Security Frameworks: From Cybersecurity to AI Governance* (5525340). SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5525340>

Shabad, V. (2025b). *Strategic Governance of Healthcare Cyber Resilience: An Enterprise Architecture Analysis of Cognitive Bias Amplification* (5643210). SSRN.

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5643210>

Shabad, V. (2026a). *Beyond Compliance: An Empirical Analysis of the "Red Queen Effect" in NHS Cyber Assurance and the Case for Ecological Rationality* (6014674). SSRN.

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6014674>

Shabad, V. (2026b). *Closing the DORA Gap: A Three-Tier Architecture for Cyber Incident Disclosure* (6524798). SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6524798>

Shabad, V. (2026c). *The Explainability Paradox: When Algorithmic Transparency Enables Gaming* (6131028). SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6131028>

Shabad, V. (2026d). When “More Data” Feels Safe but Increases Risk: A Boardroom Paradox. *BMJ Leader Blog*. <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmjleader/2026/01/26/when-more-data-feels-safe-but-increases-risk-a-boardroom-paradox-by-vsevolod-shabad/>

Shabad, V. (2026e). When silence becomes the default: what the Kent meningitis outbreak reveals about outbreak governance. *BMJ Leader Blog*.

<https://blogs.bmj.com/bmjleader/2026/03/30/when-silence-becomes-the-default-what-the-kent-meningitis-outbreak-reveals-about-outbreak-governance-by-vsevolod-shabad/>

Declarations

AI use: During the preparation of this submission, the author used Claude (Anthropic) and Gemini (Google) to structure and improve the readability and language quality of the text as a non-native English speaker. After using these tools, the author reviewed and edited the content and takes full responsibility for the content of this submission.

Competing interests: The author has no current financial interest in the outcome of this consultation. He wrote the working papers and blog posts cited under his name in this submission.

Funding: This work received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.